

Solving for Gaussian Normalization Using 3 Cartesian Dimensions Instead of the Usual Two

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Given a one dimensional Gaussian integral, a standard textbook trick is to find the normalization constant by going to two Cartesian dimensions and then converting to polar co-ordinates. This requires knowledge of the integral $\int_0^{\infty} \exp(-y) dy$. We consider here finding the normalization constant by considering three Cartesian co-ordinates and again only the integral $\int_0^{\infty} \exp(-y) dy$ (and integration by parts).

Integration Using Polar Variables for Two Cartesian Dimensions

Traditionally, a Gaussian integral is solved (in textbooks) by converting from two dimensional Cartesian to Polar co-ordinates i.e.

$$\left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \exp(-px^2/(2mT)) \right\} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \exp(-py^2/(2mT)) \right\}$$

$$= 2 \cdot 3.14 \int_0^{\infty} dp \exp(-pp/2mT) = 3.14 (2mT) \quad ((1))$$

Given that Cartesian form in ((1)) is a square of integrals, the normalization of one of them is:

$$1/\sqrt{3.14 \cdot 2mT} \quad ((2))$$

This is consistent with the normalized Gaussian integral given in (1):

$$1/\sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \sigma^2} \exp(-xx / (2 \cdot \sigma^2)) \quad ((3))$$

((2)) is a one-dimensional Gaussian.

One may note that an explicit integral was performed to find the solution ((1)).

Solving the Gaussian Integration Using Three Cartesian Co-ordinates

We suggest that one may obtain the normalization constant ((2)) by using three Cartesian co-ordinates instead of the usual two. We change variables:

$$e = pp/2m = px^2/2m + py^2/2m + pz^2/2m \quad ((4))$$

Using

$$pp \, dp \, 4 \cdot 3.14 = 4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot m \sqrt{2me} \, de = c_1 \sqrt{e} \, de \quad ((5))$$

A normalized three dimensional Gaussian then becomes

$$1 = C(T) \int_0^{\infty} c_1 \sqrt{e} \, de \exp(-e/T) \quad ((6))$$

Using $y = e/T$ shows that $C(T) = b T^{\text{power } -1.5}$ ((7)) and that:

$$1/b = (2)^{\text{power } 1.5} m^{\text{power } 1.5} 3.14 * \int_0^{\infty} dy \sqrt{y} \exp(-y) \quad ((7))$$

Given that one deals with three dimensions and that $1.5 = 3/2$ one might consider that:

$$\int_0^{\infty} dy \sqrt{y} \exp(-y) = \sqrt{3.14} * d^{\text{power } 3} \quad ((8))$$

where d is unknown.

{If we consider the two dimensional case for $m=1$ and $T=1$, this gives the full solution for the normalization constant as:

$$(2*3.14) \int_0^{\infty} dy \exp(-y) = 2* 3.14 d \quad ((9))$$

This shows that $d=1$, but we bypass this result and consider one dimension together with three dimensions as an alternative way of solving the problem.}

In the one dimensional case: ($T=1, m=1$)

$$\int_0^{\infty} dy \exp(-y) / \sqrt{2y} = d \sqrt{3.14} \sqrt{2} \quad ((10))$$

Now, one may integrate ((8)) by parts to obtain:

$$3.14 (2^{\text{power } 1.5}) \sqrt{3.14} d^{\text{power } 3} = 3.14 (2^{\text{power } 1.5}) \int_0^{\infty} dy \sqrt{y} \exp(-y) \quad ((11))$$

Then:

$$\text{LHS} = 3.14 (2^{\text{power } 1.5}) \sqrt{3.14} d^{\text{power } 3} \quad \text{RHS} = 3.14 (2^{\text{power } 1.5}) \{ .5 \sqrt{2} \} d \sqrt{3.14} \sqrt{2} \quad ((12))$$

The LHS should equal the RHS and this implies that $d^{\text{power } 3} = d$ or $d=1$.

This means that using the three dimensional approach, one has the normalization constant:

$$1/ \{ (2^{\text{power } 1.5}) (m^{\text{power } 1.5}) (T^{\text{power } 1.5}) (3.14^{\text{power } 1.5}) \} \quad ((12))$$

The one dimensional case is the cube root.

This also implies that $\int_0^{\infty} \sqrt{y} \exp(-y) dy = \sqrt{3.14}$ ((13))

Using $\Gamma(1/2) = \sqrt{3.14}$ and $\Gamma(1+1/2) = 1/2 \Gamma(1/2)$ one sees that ((13)) is $\Gamma(3/2)$. (Identities from (2)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may find the one dimensional Gaussian normalization constant by considering a product of two Gaussians, i.e. two Cartesian co-ordinates and switching to polar co-ordinates. This is a simple way to solve the problem and is given in textbooks. The only integral required is $\int_0^{\infty} dy \exp(-y)$.

Here we consider three Cartesian co-ordinates instead and find the same result by only knowing $\int_0^{\infty} dy \exp(-y)$ and the notion of integration by parts which allows one to compare the three dimensional case with the one dimensional one.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Normal_distribution
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gamma_function